

Term Paper on Benzene Production via Hydrodealkylation of Toluene

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Abstract

The major objectives of this experiment are to study the hydrodealkylation method of toluene to produce benzene and apply material and energy balance calculation over a proper hydrodealkylation plant. To achieve this goal, we have discussed the study background of hydrodealkylation of toluene, the raw materials of the plant, the process description of the plant, waste management and the environmental impact of the plant and market analysis of the plant. We have also encountered the material and energy balance calculation of this plant. Toluene hydrodealkylation converts toluene to benzene. In this hydrogen-intensive process, toluene is mixed with hydrogen and then passed over a chromium catalyst at 500–650 °C and 20–60 atm pressure. The plant mainly consists of one plug flow reactor (PFR), one pressure swing absorber (PSA) and some distillation and separation devices. The raw materials of this process are hydrogen and toluene. We expect to collect pure toluene from crude oil and synthesize hydrogen from the steam-methane reforming plant of hydrogen. We assumed a 95% pure hydrogen fresh feed stream with balanced methane. The process calculation yields all expected results which proves that the assumptions taken were relevant. The product of this plant is 99.86% benzene with balance toluene. Our plant ensures 300 tons of yearly benzene production. To perform our calculation, we have assumed that the plant runs 330 days per year and 24 hours per day. The byproduct streams contain 19% diphenyl solution with balance toluene and 56% methane with balance hydrogen solution. These byproduct streams can be later purified and converted into other compounds. The effluent hydrogen and toluene can be recycled and used in the process later. To fulfil the yearly supply requirement, we will have to ensure 2872.621kmol/hr of hydrogen feed flow rate and 546.13kmol/hr of toluene feed flow rate at operating conditions.

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Chapter One:

Study Background

Benzene is one of the most important molecules of all time in the history of human civilization. It has a fascinating history that goes back 200 years. The story is closely linked to the history of the development of chemistry. Benzene was first isolated by Michael Faraday in 1825, from the whale oil used in gaslights; he also determined that it had an empirical formula of CH.^[1] On that year Faraday published a paper at 'Philosophical Transactions of The Royal Society'. This is the world's oldest and longest-running journal. It is still in print today. The title of his paper was 'On New Compounds of Carbon and Hydrogen and Certain Other Products Obtained During Decomposition of Oil by Heat'. At that time, he named this compound 'Bicarbouret of Hydrogen'.^[2] The structure of benzene and its derivatives was a puzzle for many years. Many other compounds with similar properties to benzene were discovered in the 1800s, all having a low ratio of hydrogen to carbon. This usually indicates the presence of carbon-carbon double bonds, but these compounds did not undergo the reactions typical of alkenes under ordinary lab conditions. Since many of these molecules had pleasant aromas, they were called aromatic compounds.^[3]

In 1866, Friedrich August Kekulé proposed the cyclic structure of benzene. Since then, the term aromatic in organic chemistry used to mean that the molecule contains benzene or its structural relatives. Hence benzene is considered as one of the simplest and most important aromatic compounds. The name benzene was given by German Chemist Eilhardt Mitscherlich in 1833. He synthesized benzene in 1834, and showed it to have a molecular formula of C₆H₆.^[4] The word benzene derives historically from gum benzoin, sometimes called 'Benjamin'. Gum benzoin was known as an aromatic resin.^[5]

1.1 Overview of Benzene

Before the discovery of the various derivatives, benzene was primarily used in gasoline blending because of its octane value; and as a solvent due to its high hydrocarbon solubility. In today's modern chemical processing industry, benzene is more profitably used as a basic building block for important chemical intermediates, including plastics, fabrics, dyes, and detergents. Benzene is among the most widely produced petrochemicals in the world. Current production is approximately 37 million tons per year, while demand is projected to grow annually at 3.8%.^[6] While the demand growth has been respectable, the supply has struggled to keep up for various

reasons. The result has been a sharp rise in benzene pricing. With few alternatives for the myriad products that are made from benzene, this has led to premium pricing and is shaping a new historical trend. As the availability, quality, and uses of hydrocarbon fuels evolve over the next few decades, chemical producers will continue to look at various benzene production routes in order to satisfy demand. The derivatives of benzene are found across nearly the entire spectrum of industrial and consumer goods.

Concerns have been raised in the chemical industry regarding products that can cause physical illness when used improperly or due to severe exposure. Many refiners have responded to consumer pressures and now avoid making the benzene through hydrogenation. They have even begun destroying benzene. With the preponderance of experience and safe operation by industrial producers, and considering the tremendously favourable process economics, these refiners may need to reconsider their process configuration decisions. Benzene will continue to play an important role in the daily lives of people around the world, despite environmental concerns. The various regulations have driven down the levels of benzene in our motor fuels and restricted the emissions from our chemical plants. However, this molecule plays an important role as a building block for various common products. Benzene production should be no more hazardous than any other commodity petrochemical if due regard is paid to the recommendations of the safety stand.

1.2 Use of Benzene

Benzene is probably the most important substance in the history of human civilization. Every second compound today, that is popular or heavily used by people, contains a benzene ring. Benzene is used as a chemical intermediate for the production of many important industrial compounds, such as styrene (polystyrene and synthetic rubber), phenol (phenolic resins), cyclohexane (nylon), aniline (dyes), alkylbenzenes (detergents), and chlorobenzenes. Benzene is a widely used industrial chemical and is a major part of gasoline.[7] Some other uses of Benzene include making plastics, synthetic fibres, rubber lubricants, dyes, resins, detergents, drugs and more. Some popular ones are mentioned and discussed below.

1.2.1 Regular Use of Benzene

As a Solvent: Benzene is commonly used as a solvent in many industrial, commercial and research projects. Manufacturers use products which contain benzene as solvents in various production stages and it is used in manufacturing chemical and plastic products. A few examples include

resins, synthetic products such as nylon, Styrofoam and others. Benzene is also used in the production of asphalt that is used by roofing and paving companies.

Production of Rubber: Benzene is commonly used in the manufacturing of tires and rubbers. Manufacturers use products containing benzene as a solvent in many manufacturing processes. For instance, the adhesive used to glue soles to shoes contains a high amount of benzene.

Paints and Printing Industries: Most of the products used in printing industries contain benzene. Benzene is primarily found in products that are used to clean the printing equipment. The use of benzene in the cleaning products makes the printing equipment long-lasting and properly functional. Many other printing products such as inks and dyes are manufactured using benzene. Most paints, such as spray paints, base and top coat paints, lacquers, stains and sealers contain a significant part of benzene to keep them in liquid form. These products are used by professional painters in painting homes, buildings and even automobile parts.

Benzene as a Fuel: Benzene is an essential product used in the production of gasoline. Benzene forms a large part of crude oil, and most of the products manufactured by oil refineries contain benzene in them. Benzene is also used in the production of lubricants which are used for the maintenance of heavy machinery in the production industries. Due to its abundant availability in nature, benzene is also used as an industrial fuel. It is mainly used in the production of asphalt, which is used as an adhesive in roofing and paving companies.

Auto Repairs: The solvents that are used in auto repair facilities in automobile industries contain benzene. The solvents containing benzene are used for cleaning the hydraulic systems, fuel system compartments and braking system. The use of benzene helps dissolve the grease that builds upon the automobile parts, and it also does not harm the metal.

1.2.2 Industrial use of Benzene

Benzene finds various industrial applications due to its properties as a versatile solvent and chemical intermediate. Here are some specific industrial uses of benzene:

1. Production of Styrene: Benzene is a key raw material in the production of styrene, which is used to manufacture polystyrene, a widely used plastic in packaging, insulation, consumer goods, and construction materials.

2. Production of Cumene: Benzene is used in the production of cumene, which is then oxidized to produce phenol and acetone. Phenol is a precursor in the production of resins, adhesives, and pharmaceuticals.

3. Production of Cyclohexane: Benzene is hydrogenated to produce cyclohexane, which is used in the production of nylon, as well as in the manufacturing of solvents, plasticizers, and other chemicals.

4. Production of Nitrobenzene: Benzene is nitrated to produce nitrobenzene, which is used in the production of aniline, which in turn is a precursor for dyes, pharmaceuticals, and rubber chemicals.

5. Production of Alkylbenzenes: Benzene is alkylated to produce alkylbenzenes, which are used as detergents, surfactants, and lubricating oil additives.

6. Production of Polycarbonate: Benzene is a precursor in the production of bisphenol A, which is used in the manufacture of polycarbonate plastics and epoxy resins.

7. Synthetic Rubber Production: Benzene is used in the production of synthetic rubber, such as styrene-butadiene rubber (SBR) and polybutadiene rubber (PBR), which are used in tires, hoses, belts, and various other rubber products.

8. Laboratory and Research: Benzene is commonly used as a solvent and reagent in laboratory research and chemical synthesis.

9. Pharmaceuticals and Fine Chemicals: Benzene and its derivatives are important intermediates in the synthesis of pharmaceuticals, dyes, fragrances, pesticides, and other specialty chemicals.

1.3 Chemical Structure of Benzene

Benzene is a clear flammable liquid with a boiling point of 80.1°C and with the molecular formula C₆H₆. [8] The benzene molecule is composed of six carbon atoms joined in a planar hexagonal ring with one hydrogen atom attached to each. Benzene is a natural constituent of petroleum and is one of the elementary petrochemicals. Due to the cyclic continuous pi bonds between the carbon atoms, benzene is classed as an aromatic hydrocarbon. X ray diffraction shows that all six carbon-carbon bonds in benzene are of the same length, at 140 picometres (pm). The C–C bond lengths are greater than a double bond (135 pm) but shorter than a single bond (147 pm). This intermediate distance is caused by electron delocalization: the electrons for C=C bonding are distributed equally between

each of the six carbon atoms. Benzene has fewer hydrogen atoms than the corresponding parent alkane, hexane, which has 14. It and cyclohexane have a similar structure, only the ring of delocalized electrons and the loss of one hydrogen per carbon distinguishes it from cyclohexane. The molecule is planar.[9] The molecular orbital description involves the formation of three delocalized π orbitals spanning all six carbon atoms, while the valence bond description involves a superposition of resonance structures.[10] This stability likely contributes to the peculiar molecular and chemical properties known as aromaticity. To reflect the delocalized nature of the bonding, benzene is often depicted with a circle inside a hexagonal arrangement of carbon atoms.[11] The benzene structure proposed by Friedrich Karl Johannes Thiele is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Benzene structure proposed by Friedrich Karl Johannes Thiele (1899).[12]

1.4 Grades of Benzene

Benzene is classified as a hazardous waste by the EPA under subtitle C of the Resource and Recovery Act (RCRA). Effective Sept. 25, 1990, solid wastes containing more than 0.5 mg/mL benzene must be treated in accordance with applicable RCRA regulations. Benzene emissions and effluent streams from petroleum refineries or benzene processing plants are also subject to strict federal regulations. Several different grades of benzene are commercially available. The most common grades are benzene 535, benzene 485 (nitration grade), benzene 545, and thiophene-free benzene. Benzene is classified as a flammable liquid and should be stored away from any potential source of ignition. Benzene is shipped by rail tank cars, trucks, barges, and tankers. Because of the flammability, toxicity, and volatility of benzene, transfers from one vessel to another are conducted in closed systems. [7] Some major grades and grading criteria are mentioned below.

Benzene 535: Benzene 535 is a grade of refined benzene. ASTM D2359-19 is the standard specification for refined benzene 535. This specification covers tests to determine the following properties of refined benzene 535:

- Minimum purity,
- Maximum toluene content,
- Maximum sulfur content,
- Maximum thiophene content.[7]

Benzene 485: Benzene 485 is a refined grade of benzene with a solidification point of 4.85°C and a distillation range of no more than 1.0°C. It is one of the most common grades of benzene. [13]

Thiophene free Benzene: This grade of benzene has the only requirement and that is, the solution must be thiophene free. Thiophene-free benzene is often needed in laboratories, especially in small quantities. [14]

Technical Grade: This grade is readily available in Sona enterprise, India. The purity of benzene of this grade is 99.9%. The current cost of this product is ₹56/ Kilogram. [15]

Benzene 545: The standard specification for refined benzene-545 is ASTM D4734. The standard covers benzene-545 and covers tests to determine its property requirements. It is a flammable liquid. [7]

Benzene 545: This grade is readily available in Molekula Group, Spain. The purity of benzene of this grade is 99.7%-100%. The current cost of this product is £62.10/Litre. [16]

The summary of benzene grades is shown below.

Table 1: Different grades of benzene and their grading criteria.

Name of the Grade	Grading Criteria	Reference
Benzene 535	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Minimum purity • Maximum toluene content • Maximum sulfur content • Maximum thiophene content 	[7]
Benzene 484	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • solidification point: 4.85°C 	[13]

	• Distillation range: 1.0°C	
Thiophene free grade	Thiophene composition should be zero	[14]
Technical grade	Purity of benzene is 99.9%	[15]
Benzene SHHPLC grade	Purity of benzene is 99.7%-100%	[16]
Benzene 545	ASTM D4734	[7]

1.5 Benzene Production Process

Industrial production process of benzene yields a wide range of variation. The research and invention of new type of benzene production process is still ongoing. There are thousands of patents over benzene production methodology throughout the world. Yet, most of the procedures can majorly divided in four chemical processes.

1. Catalytic reforming,
2. Toluene hydrodealkylation,
3. Toluene disproportionation and
4. Steam cracking.

1. Catalytic Reforming

In catalytic reforming, a mixture of hydrocarbons with boiling points between 60°C and 200°C is blended with hydrogen gas. Then the effluent is exposed to a bifunctional platinum chloride or rhenium chloride catalyst at 500–525 °C and pressures ranging from 8–50 atm. Under these conditions, aliphatic hydrocarbons form rings and lose hydrogen to become aromatic hydrocarbons. The aromatic products of the reaction are then separated from the reaction mixture by extraction with any one of a number of solvents, including diethyl glycol or sulfonate, and benzene is then separated from the other aromatics by distillation. The extraction step of aromatics from the reformat is designed to produce aromatics with lowest non-aromatic components. The main reactions that can occur during catalytic steam reforming of toluene are:

Methane steam reforming: $\text{CH}_4 + \text{H}_2\text{O} \leftrightarrow \text{CO} + 3\text{H}_2$

Boudouard reaction: $2\text{CO} \leftrightarrow \text{CO}_2 + \text{C}$

In similar fashion to this catalytic reforming, UOP and BP commercialized a method from LPG to aromatics.[17]

2. Toluene hydrodealkylation

Toluene hydrodealkylation converts toluene to benzene. In this hydrogen-intensive process, toluene is mixed with hydrogen, then passed over a chromium, molybdenum, or platinum oxide catalyst at 500–650 °C and 20–60 atm pressure. Sometimes, higher temperatures are used instead of a catalyst. Under these conditions, toluene undergoes dealkylation to benzene and methane:

This irreversible reaction is accompanied by an equilibrium side reaction that produces diphenyl at higher temperature:

If the raw material stream contains much non-aromatic components (paraffins or naphthenes), those are likely decomposed to lower hydrocarbons such as methane, which increases the consumption of hydrogen. A typical reaction yield exceeds 95%. Sometimes, xylenes and heavier aromatics are used in place of toluene, with similar efficiency.

3. Toluene disproportionation

Toluene disproportionation (TDP) is the conversion of toluene to benzene and xylene. Given that demand for para-xylene (p-xylene) substantially exceeds demand for other xylene isomers, a refinement of the TDP process called Selective TDP (STDP) may be used. In this process, the xylene stream exiting the TDP unit is approximately 90% p-xylene. In some systems, even the benzene-to-xylenes ratio is modified to favor xylenes.

4. Steam cracking

Steam cracking is the process for producing ethylene and other alkenes from aliphatic hydrocarbons. Depending on the feedstock used to produce the olefins, steam cracking can produce

a benzene-rich liquid by-product called pyrolysis gasoline. Pyrolysis gasoline can be blended with other hydrocarbons as a gasoline additive, or routed through an extraction process to recover benzene, toluene or xylenes.

1.6 Advantages and Disadvantages of HDA Process

Hydrodealkylation (HDA) offers several advantages and disadvantages:

1.6.1 Advantages of HDA Process

1. High Selectivity: HDA is highly selective for the dealkylation of alkyl aromatic compounds, leading to high yields of benzene with minimal formation of byproducts. [18]

2. Efficiency: The process is efficient due to the use of catalysts, which accelerate the reaction rates and allow for lower operating temperatures and pressures compared to non-catalytic methods.

3. Economic Benefits: HDA can be economically advantageous because of its high yield and selectivity, which can lead to cost savings in production processes.

4. Environmental Impact: Compared to alternative methods, HDA often has a lower environmental impact. It typically operates under milder conditions, reducing energy consumption and emissions.

5. Catalytic Efficiency: The use of catalysts enhances the efficiency of the process. Catalysts facilitate the reaction by providing an alternative pathway with lower activation energy, thus speeding up the conversion of alkyl aromatics to benzene.

1.6.2 Disadvantages of HDA Process

1. Catalyst Cost: Catalysts used in HDA processes can be expensive, which may increase the overall production cost.

2. Catalyst Degradation: Catalysts can degrade over time due to fouling or poisoning, which may necessitate frequent regeneration or replacement, adding to operational costs.

3. Complexity: HDA processes can be technically complex, requiring careful control of reaction conditions and catalyst properties to optimize performance and prevent undesired side reactions.

4. Feedstock Limitations: HDA is typically applied to specific feedstocks, such as toluene or xylenes, which limits its applicability to other types of hydrocarbons.

Overall, while hydrodealkylation offers significant advantages in terms of selectivity, efficiency, and environmental impact, it also presents challenges related to catalyst management and process complexity. These factors must be carefully considered in the design and operation of HDA units in industrial settings.

1.7 Health Hazard of Benzene

It has several effects like headache, instability, convulsions, unconsciousness and irritations. Depending on the exposure, it can have both acute and chronic effects. And this can happen when Benzene is taken in through the mouth or inhaled through the air or absorbed by the skin. People are usually exposed to benzene when they fill their car with gasoline or while using household items that contain benzene or contaminated water. The hazard symbols for SHHPLC grade grade benzene are:

Figure 2: Health hazard signs of benzene.[16]

People are exposed to benzene primarily by breathing air that contains the chemical. Workers in industries that produce or use benzene may be exposed to the highest levels of the chemical, although federal and state regulations have reduced these exposures in recent decades. Similarly, limits on the amount of benzene allowed in gasoline have contributed to reduced exposures. Mainstream cigarette smoke is another source of benzene exposure, accounting for about half of the total U.S. population exposure to this chemical. Among smokers, 90 percent of benzene exposures come from smoking. Benzene may also be found in glues, adhesives, cleaning products, and paint strippers. Outdoor air contains low levels of benzene from secondhand tobacco smoke, gasoline fumes, motor vehicle exhaust, and industrial emissions.[19] Besides, people who live near

places where benzene is used or was spilled or disposed of in the past can be exposed to benzene from drinking water. If levels are high enough, people can also breathe in benzene vapors that come out of the water when it is used to shower, bath, and run the dishwasher and washing machine.

Chapter two:

**Raw Materials and Sources
of Raw Materials**

2. Raw Materials and Sources of Raw Materials

HDA process of benzene production is very famous throughout the world. It is not a different scenario in Bangladesh either. In Bangladesh, SPL, Crescent Chemical Limited are the pioneers of benzene production. They also use the HDA process in benzene production. The raw materials of benzene production through hydrodealkylation are more available in our country than the other methods. The major raw materials of benzene production plant through hydrodealkylation are toluene and hydrogen. Toluene is extracted from crude oil. It is readily available in the market of Bangladesh. Besides, hydrogen is often reformed by steam-methane reforming. Natural gas is very available in Bangladesh. In addition, the available natural gas does not contain sulfur compounds. This is another advantage for us while producing benzene. While designing the hydrogen plant, we generally don't need to establish any desulfurization unit in our plant. Hence, our establishment expenditure is saved.

2.1 Toluene

Toluene is a naturally occurring compound derived primarily from petroleum or petrochemical processes. It is a common component in gasoline, glues, and paint products. It is a liquid, which is colourless, water-insoluble and smells like paint thinners. The compound was first isolated in 1837 through a distillation of pine oil by Pierre Joseph Pelletier and Filip Neriusz Walter. He named it Rétinnaphte.[20] In 1841, Henri Étienne Sainte-Claire Deville isolated a hydrocarbon from balsam of Tolu. Deville recognized as similar to Walter's Rétinnaphte and to benzene; hence he called the new hydrocarbon Benzoène.[21] In 1843, Jöns Jacob Berzelius recommended the name Toluin. In 1850, French chemist Auguste Cahours isolated from a distillate of wood a hydrocarbon which he recognized as similar to Deville's benzoène and which Cahours named toluène.

2.2 Properties of Toluene

The chemical formula of toluene is $C_6H_5CH_3$. Its boiling point is $111^\circ C$. The melting point of toluene is $-95^\circ C$. The density of toluene is 0.87 g/mol and the molecular weight of toluene is 92.141 g/mol . Toluene reacts as a normal aromatic hydrocarbon in electrophilic aromatic

substitution. Because the methyl group has greater electron-releasing properties than a hydrogen atom in the same position, toluene is more reactive than benzene toward electrophiles. Toluene reacts as an aromatic hydrocarbon in an electrophilic aromatic substitution reaction. Because the methyl group has greater electron-releasing properties than a hydrogen atom in the same position. Toluene is more reactive than benzene toward electrophiles. Toluene undergoes sulfonation and as a result, it gives p-toluene sulfonic acid, and chlorination by Cl_2 in the presence of FeCl_3 to provide ortho and para isomers of chlorotoluene. Though, it has a methyl side chain, it is susceptible to oxidation. Toluene reacts with Potassium permanganate to yield benzoic acid, and with chromyl chloride to yield benzaldehyde alike Etard reaction. The methyl group in toluene undergoes halogenation under free-radical conditions. For instance, N-bromosuccinimide is heated with toluene in the presence of AIBN to produce benzyl bromide. The same conversion can be affected by elemental bromine in the presence of Ultra-violet light or even sunlight. Toluene can easily be brominated by treating it with HBr and H_2O_2 in the presence of light. The methyl group in toluene undergoes deprotonation only if it is with very strong bases. Its pK_a is estimated to approximately be 41. Complete hydrogenation of toluene gives methylcyclohexane. This reaction requires a high pressure of hydrogen and also a catalyst.

2.3 Source of Toluene

Toluene is produced from petroleum as an aromatic mixture with benzene and xylene primarily by catalytic reforming and pyrolytic cracking. Catalytic reforming processes account for about 87% of the total amount of toluene produced in the USA. This process involves the dehydrogenation of selected petroleum fractions containing abundant naphthenic hydrocarbons to yield a mixture of aromatics and paraffins. Reforming processes are used to produce a benzene-toluene-xylene reformate from which the individual aromatics are recovered by distillation, washing with nitric acid and re-distillation. Only a small fraction of the reformate is used for isolation of the toluene; the bulk of the unseparated toluene in the reformate is used for gasoline blending.

The second largest source of toluene is from pyrolysis gasoline, formed as a by-product during pyrolytic cracking (steam cracking) of heavier hydrocarbons for the manufacture of olefins. Toluene is isolated from pyrolysis gasoline by distillation, removal of olefins and di-olefins and re-distillation. Toluene is also obtained as a by-product during styrene manufacture when ethylbenzene is dehydrogenated. The toluene isolated from the by-product is used for gasoline

blending or as feed for benzene manufacture by the hydrodealkylation process. The production of toluene from coke-oven operations is minimal.[22]

The amounts of isolated toluene (and of total toluene) produced in these different ways in the USA in 1978 were as follows: from catalytic reformat, 3.6 (29.5) million tonnes; from pyrolysis gasoline, 376.8 (708) thousand tonnes; as a styrene biproduct, 99.8 (145) thousand tonnes; and derived from coal, 65.8 (79.5) thousand tonnes. These quantities represent a total of 4.2 (30) million tonnes.[23]

Western Europe and Japan are also major producers of this compound. In 1980, over 85% of the toluene produced in the world was accounted for by the USA, western Europe and Japan. In Japan and western Europe, toluene is produced mainly from pyrolysis gasoline. In all three areas, coke-oven light oil provided less than 10% of the toluene supply in 1980.

Table 2: The amounts of toluene produced in different ways in the USA at 1978.[23]

Toluene Production Process	Toluene Isolated	Toluene Available	Unit of estimation
Catalytic reforming	3.6	29.5	Million Metric Tons
Pyrolysis of gasoline	376.8	708	Thousand Metric Tons
Styrene biproduct	99.8	145	Thousand Metric Tons
Coal	65.8	79.5	Thousand Metric Tons

Figure 3: The amounts of toluene produced in different ways in the USA at 1978.

2.4 Hydrogen Production Process

2.4.1 Steam methane reforming with and without carbon capture and storage

The Steam-methane Reforming (SMR) process involves two crucial steps outlined in Equations (1) and (2):

Initially, natural gas, mainly composed of methane, undergoes high-temperature steam reforming (Eq. (1)), yielding carbon monoxide (CO), hydrogen, and unreacted natural gas. Subsequently, additional steam reacts with CO in the WGSR (Eq. (2)), generating more hydrogen while converting CO to CO₂. Overall, the process boasts an efficiency of around 76% (CH₄ to H₂ based on higher heating value). In our process, we have used this method. Our efficiency of the reformer unit is assumed to be 70%.[24]

SMR emits substantial CO₂ emissions. This concern is mitigated by Carbon Capture and Storage (CCS). In this system, flue gases are separated, with 90% of CO₂ absorbed using monoethanolamine - MEA. The treated flue gas, now devoid of CO₂, is released into the atmosphere. The captured CO₂ is then thermally desorbed, compressed to 110 bar, and stored, resulting in an energy efficiency of 68%.[25] The additional energy consumption for CCS, equivalent to 3.79 MJ CH₄/kg CO₂ captured, aligns with literature values (3.6 to 4 MJ CH₄/kg CO₂ captured), with CO₂ emissions from the capture process estimated at 0.21 kg CO₂/kg CO₂ captured. [25]

SMR and SMR with CCS share similar supply chains but differ in fuel usage and emissions. Enhanced capture rates above 90% could alleviate impacts on human health and ecosystems by reducing direct CO₂ emissions, a major contributor to these categories. Operational and capital expenditures correlate with capture rates, with higher rates demanding greater fuel duty and additional equipment. However, deep decarbonization (>90%) costs remain uncertain. [25]

Replacing MEA with alternative capture methods, such as adsorption using Metal-Organic Frameworks (MOFs), offers potential environmental benefits and cost reductions. MOFs, characterized by high surface area and pore volumes, hold promise for improved capture and storage capabilities, potentially overcoming limitations of conventional storage methods. Moreover, resource depletion, primarily from natural gas feedstock (70%)[26] [27] and process fuel requirements (30%)[28], contributes significantly to environmental externalities. Integration of waste energy streams could reduce the latter contribution, albeit with additional integration costs. While SMR with CCS currently presents the most cost-effective solution, opportunities for reduced environmental impacts remain limited in the medium to long term. [27]

2.4.2 Methane pyrolysis

Pyrolysis processes decompose hydrocarbons into solid carbon and hydrogen (Eq. (3)) at high temperatures (thermally or catalytically). As no oxygen is present, no carbon oxides are formed, potentially eliminating the need for secondary processing steps such as the WGS, reducing the CAPEX and operational expenditures (OPEX) compared to SMR. The higher H₂ concentration of the product gas stream also has considerable potential for minimizing downstream clean-up processes. The cost of methane pyrolysis is strongly dependent on the processing route, the price of natural gas, and the by-product solid carbon. Several pyrolysis processes including plasma-

based, high-temperature thermal (thermal black), solid catalytic, and molten metal catalytic systems. Here we assume a catalytic molten metal process. From a carbon-storage perspective, pyrolysis processes offer the advantage of storing a solid C-product as opposed to gaseous CO₂.

Methane pyrolysis is the second cheapest total cost route. It emits less direct CO₂ emissions and less FPMF than SMR, which leads to lower human health and ecosystem quality impacts. However, methane pyrolysis consumes more natural gas per unit of H₂ than SMR, which increases the resources depletion costs. In this route, human health and ecosystem quality account for 17% and 12%, respectively, of the TCH. These impacts are mainly driven by the natural gas supply chain emissions and the required heat for the process, which is assumed to be sourced from natural gas. Notably, the sweetening of natural gas and the fugitive methane emissions are the main contributors to the natural gas supply chain emissions. The higher supply chain impacts due to larger natural gas consumption are offset by the lower direct emissions of methane pyrolysis. Other means of heat sources could further reduce the environmental impacts. For the resources depletion category, about 18% of the natural gas is used for heating in the process with an overall efficiency of 53%. Finding alternative heat sources could help reduce the impacts in this category, although this would likely increase the process costs. Cost reduction opportunities for methane pyrolysis are mostly direct production cost-related (38% of the TCH). Similarly, as with SMR and SMR with carbon capture and storage, there might be limited opportunities for additional reductions in externalities. The levelised cost of hydrogen of this route is highly sensitive to the natural gas prices and the opportunities for selling the solid carbon produced. For the current analysis, no value was assigned to the solid carbon; hence, finding potential carbon markets and applications would bring the levelised cost of hydrogen down. Currently, solid carbon produced by high-temperature methane pyrolysis is commercially used in tires and electrical equipment; however, the physical and electrical properties determine its suitability to higher value market applications. Another important aspect to highlight is that this technology still exhibits a relatively low TRL, with only early-stage pilot plants in operation. Thus, additional technological developments and learning curves may further reduce its TCH.[29]

2.4.3. Coal gasification with and without carbon capture and storage

In this route, coal is partially oxidised in the presence of oxygen or air to produce a syngas mixture (CO, H₂, CO₂, and unreacted CH₄) at high temperatures (800–1300 °C) and pressures of 30–70 bar. The syngas is further enriched by the WGSR to recover more hydrogen. Coal gasification is less efficient than SMR (55%) but offers higher single-train capacities. The overall reaction is presented in Eq. (4). The lower carbon to hydrogen ratio in coal relative to natural gas results in significantly higher direct CO₂ emissions from the process. The inventory data for both coal gasification routes (without and with CCS) are taken from the works by Ruthowski and Vickers, respectively.

Despite the low costs of the coal feedstock, coal gasification has the highest TCH [\$12.65 /kgH₂] because of the high environmental externalities. It has 88% of the overall TCH. When coupled with carbon capture and storage, the TCH for coal gasification [\$10.59 /kgH₂] is improved by 16%, primarily driven by the decrease in the human health and ecosystem quality impacts linked to lower direct CO₂ emissions (81% reduction with capture rates of 86.85%). Carbon capture and storage, however, cannot reduce the environmental impacts associated with the coal feed. These are mainly linked to the methane emissions in the mining and pre-treatment stages. Hence, the potential improvements of carbon capture and storage are mainly focused on the direct emissions of the gasification plant.[30]

2.4.4 Biomass gasification with and without carbon capture and storage

Biomass resources can be used for hydrogen production. Similar to coal, gasification is the most convenient pathway for biomass feedstocks as biomass gasification provides the highest yield taking place at high temperatures, typically at 500–1400 °C. The overall reaction is shown in Eq. (5).

There is a wealth of interdependent research related to LCAs that investigate biomass-to-hydrogen processes differing in the biomass feedstock and system configurations. This study considers poplar and covers the plantation phase of the biomass, fertilisers requirements, and water consumption following the work by Peters et al. Biomass gasification can be also integrated with

CCS to yield a negative carbon balance. The inventory data for both biomass gasification systems without and with CCS are taken from Susmozas et al.

Both the LCOH and externality impacts are high contributors of the TCH for the biomass gasification and biomass gasification with carbon capture and storage technologies. Carbon capture and storage reduces the impact on human health substantially, as it is strongly linked to CO₂ emissions. In contrast, the impact on ecosystem quality is not significantly reduced when deploying carbon capture and storage because it is mainly connected to the biomass feedstock due to the high contributions of the water consumption and land use impacts. The LCOH estimates for biomass gasification with carbon capture and storage available in the literature are scarce. Only two LCOH values were found. The average of those two values used in the nominal case represents 32% of the TCH of this technology. Since the TRL of this route is still at the research phase, there is significant uncertainty in the cost estimations in the medium to long terms. Hence, this topic should be the subject of further investigation. Notably, our analysis is quite sensitive to the biomass feedstock type as land use impacts, water consumption, fertilisers for feedstock plantation, and the transport of the biomass to the point-of-conversion vary spatially. Hence, the former information should be taken into consideration when performing further studies in biomass-based hydrogen production pathways. The obtained results are aligned with previous studies concerning the midpoint impacts, i.e., biomass gasification emits approximately 0.39 kgCO₂/kg H₂ and 14.63 kg CO₂/kg H₂ when equipped with carbon capture and storage. For the ecosystem quality impact, the biomass feedstock is the main contributor to the total impact due to the land utilisation and water consumption in the biomass plantations. Despite the potentially low environmental impacts of biomass gasification with carbon capture and storage, one of the main limitations of biomass routes is the relatively low hydrogen yields from biomass. [31] [32]

2.4.5. Electrolysis-based routes

High purity hydrogen can be produced from water electrolysis as described by Eq. (6). Alkaline and proton exchange membrane (PEM) electrolyzers operate at low temperatures (70–90 °C), while solid oxide electrolysis cells can work at high temperatures (650–850 °C). In this study, a PEM electrolyser is considered as it provides a faster start, higher flexibility and can work with intermittent power technologies such as solar and wind, attaining an efficiency as high as 85% . Furthermore, the PEM electrolyser produces hydrogen at 30 bar, which enables a consistent

comparison between the investigated production routes. Our study compares electricity from nuclear, wind, and solar to cover the electrolyser’s energy needs. The inventory data for the electrolysis process is taken from Colella et al.

Electrolysis-based hydrogen may benefit substantially from future cost reductions. Bearing this in mind, wind and nuclear electrolysis would emerge as potentially attractive options because their TCH is 4–18% higher than the TCH of SMR. Consequently, a decline in electricity costs and/or the capital investment of the electrolyser may make them economically competitive. Environmental costs are mainly driven by the electricity source – wind, nuclear and solar PV. Although the electrolysis process has zero direct emissions, the supply chain emissions of each electricity source are not negligible. Opportunities for reducing the environmental impacts further might be very limited for the case of wind and nuclear, where externalities represent, in turn, a small percentage of the TCH (nearly 14%). For solar PV, the environmental impacts are dominated by the manufacturing phase of the panels, currently made of crystalline silicon. Hence, reducing the required materials of a panel or finding alternative materials with lower embodied emissions would improve the environmental performance of this route. The LCOH is highly dependent on the electricity cost, the electrolyzer’s capital cost, and the capacity factor of the power technology. The capital cost of nuclear power plants, as well as the cost of the uranium fuel, are the main dominant factors in the nuclear route to hydrogen. This is reflected in a range of levelised cost of electricity. Furthermore, this route benefits from the clean nature of the uranium source and its higher capacity factor compared to wind and solar PV.[33] [34] [35]

Figure 2 compares between the production costs of different hydrogen production plants. For the uncertainty analysis of externalities, the boxplot bars represent the 95% confidence interval assuming that the uncertain parameters follow lognormal distributions. The dot represents the mean TCH and the red line represents the median. HH refers to the monetised human health indicator, EQ refers to the monetised ecosystem quality indicator, RD refers to the monetised resources depletion and LCOH refers to the levelised cost of hydrogen. All indicators are expressed in USD2019 per kg H₂.

Figure 4: Comparison of production costs among different hydrogen production plants.

[36]

2.5 Uses of Hydrogen

Hydrogen is a viable alternative energy source. It is also a raw material with numerous industrial applications. It is used in the production of ammonia, which is required for making fertilizer and plastics. Oil refineries also use hydrogen to remove sulphur from crude oil (hydrotreating) and to convert heavier hydrocarbons into lighter hydrocarbons (hydrocracking) and so obtain more gasoline from crude oil.

1. From grey to green hydrogen: Dutch industry generates 800,000 tonnes of hydrogen annually using the Steam Methane Reforming (SMR) method. Natural gas is converted into hydrogen at high temperatures. The process to produce this so-called grey hydrogen is not ideal as seven million tonnes of carbon dioxide are emitted every year. These emissions can be reduced significantly by switching to hydrogen generated by electrolysis.

2. Natural gas replacement: In the chemical industry, in blast furnaces and in refineries, many processes require a high temperature for the required reactions to take place. At present, such temperatures are achieved by the combustion of natural gas. Hydrogen also burns at a high temperature and is a viable alternative in applications requiring a temperature of more than 250°C.

3. Energy buffering: The sustainable generation of energy from renewable sources is not at a constant rate so supply and demand are not always in balance. Power to Gas (P2G) systems make it possible to store excess energy. For seasonal storage, energy buffering is more useful than battery storage (more suited to short term storage). The hydrogen produced in a P2G system could be used in a controllable gas plant to generate energy as needed.

2.6 Natural Gas Resource in Bangladesh

Natural gas is the most important indigenous source of energy that has been continuously produced and consumed in significant quantities since 1970. About 75% of the commercial energy of the country comes from natural gas. So far 26 gas fields have been discovered of which two of the gas fields are located in offshore area. Though Bangladesh has considerable amount of gas yet it is not enough for 50 more years at current extraction and demand rate. Natural gas is the most important fuel for Bangladesh, both in terms of energy and diversity of use. Natural gas burns more cleanly than other fuels, such as oil and coal, and produces less carbon dioxide per unit of energy released. For an equivalent amount of heat, burning natural gas produces about 30% less carbon-dioxide than burning petroleum and about 45% less than burning coal. Bangladesh Oil, Gas and Mineral Resources Corporation, Petrobangla, is entrusted with the responsibilities of the gas and coal sectors of Bangladesh. Subsidiaries under Petrobangla are responsible for exploration, production, transmission, distribution and marketing of natural gas to the end users.

Natural gas from Bangladesh is very pure, with about 95% to 99% methane and almost no sulphur. The average compositions are 97.33% methane, 1.72-% ethane, 0.35% propane and 0.19% higher hydrocarbons. Gas in most of the fields is dry, but in a few fields, it is wet, with considerable amounts of condensate, eg at Beanibazar (16 bbl/mmcf), Jalalabad (15 bbl/mmcf), and Kailashtila (13 bbl/mmcf). The total condensate reserve in the country is estimated at about 65 million barrels. Geological evidence suggests that in addition to the hydrocarbon gas already discovered, the prospect of further gas discovery in the country is bright. Natural gas plays a vital role in the economic development of the country.

Gas is the main source of commercial energy. It plays a vital role in the economic growth of Bangladesh. The natural gas consuming sectors in Bangladesh are i) Power, ii) Industry, iii) Fertilizer, iv) Captive power, v) Domestic, vi) Commercial, and vii) Transportation (CNG). The major consumers of gas are the power and industrial sectors, which account for 43% and 17%

respectively. Per capita primary commercial energy consumption in Bangladesh is still one of the lowest in the world: 205 (kg of oil equivalent per capita) in Bangladesh compared to 482 and 614 in Pakistan and India respectively in 2011. Hence, the real potential of natural gas has yet to be realized for the economic development of Bangladesh.

To meet increasing demand of natural gas, production of gas has been increasing every year. But the consumption of natural gas in the country in the last 15 years has been much more than the discovery of natural gas which is a concerning issue.

Figure 5: Historical production of gas.

[37]

Bangladesh being one of the world's most densely populated countries has been facing supply to demand gap for natural gas for a long time. Among all the countries which use natural gas, Bangladesh ranks at 34th position. In Bangladesh, natural gas is mainly used for power generation, urea fertilizer production, industrial process heating, captive power generation, and household cooking. It has also been used as a fuel vehicle in the form of compressed natural gas (CNG) since 2005. The pie chart shows the consumption of natural gas by different sectors in the year 2013-14.

Figure 6: Use of gas in different sectors

[38]

Power generation as expected is the dominant sector and industrial sector, together with fertilizer and captive power uses about 40% of the total gas which is the second largest share. CNG sector had a modest beginning with only 1.3% during 2005-06, but rapidly increased to the current level of 5%. Domestic consumption of gas also takes a large share of total consumed gas and this is a sector which has hardly an alternative source to gas. With increasing population and urbanization, the use of domestic use of gas is expected to increase. Historical consumption of natural gas by different sectors has been shown in line chart.

Figure 7: Historical consumption of gas in different sectors.

[27]

2.7 Major Uses of Natural Gas in Bangladesh

Since Natural gas is the most mentionable natural resource, it is widely used throughout the country. Some of the major uses of natural gas has been mentioned below.

Industrial Sector: The rapid industrialization has resulted in remarkable growth in the gas demand of the industrial sector. The major industries of Bangladesh which consume natural gas are textile and leather, iron & steel, food processing, beverages & tobacco, non-metallic minerals, chemicals, pulp, paper & print, non-ferrous metal, machinery and some non-specified industry. But newer

industries are emerging, some existing ones are flourishing and some are diminishing. Therefore, the industrial sector is hard to define in terms of energy consumption. Relatively small increase in the number of these industries can have a significant impact on the overall scenario. As of 2013 about 17% of produced natural gas was consumed by this sector.

Electricity Generation: Bangladesh's power sector is mostly dependent on supply of natural gas. Almost 86% power plants use natural gas as their fuel. As a result, almost 40% of gas produced is used in this sector. Bangladesh's installed electric generation capacity was 10416 MW in June, 2014, only three-fourth of which is considered to be 'available'. Nearly 800 MW of power could not be availed from the power plants due to shortage of gas supply. Only 62% of the population has access to electricity with a per capital availability of 321 kWh per year. Electricity production from natural gas sources in Bangladesh was 91.5% as of 2011. Its highest value over the past 42 years from 2011 was 91.5% in 2011, while its lowest value was 34.69% in 1973. Electricity production from natural gas sources (kWh) in Bangladesh was last measured at 40308000000 in 2011, according to the World Bank. As the power sector is dangerously dependent on natural gas, decentralization strategies are under research.

CNG Sector: Compressed natural gas (CNG) as a vehicle fuel was first introduced to Bangladesh in 1982 through a World Bank pilot project. CNG was promoted by the government in 2005 to address the severe air pollution in Dhaka during the 90's. It had a modest beginning with only 1.3% natural gas consumption in the initial year, but quickly became popular and increased to the current level of 5.3% rapidly. Its growth surpassed all predictions. Though CNG sector is still rising, it is expected to come to a steady position within a few years due to market saturation, price hike and restriction on dispensing time.

Fertilizer Productions: Bangladesh has a large agrarian base with 76 percent of total population living in the rural areas and 90 percent of the rural population directly related with agriculture. Fertilizer is considered to be one of the main inputs for increasing crop yields and farm profit for any country. Fertilizer consumption (% of fertilizer production) in Bangladesh was last measured at 231.51 in 2009, according to the World Bank. Fertilizer consumption measures the quantity of plant nutrients used per unit of arable land. Fertilizer products cover nitrogenous, potash, and phosphate fertilizers (including ground rock phosphate).

Urea is one of the most used fertilizer which is made from ammonia (NH_3), produced by the HaberBosch process. In this energy-intensive process, natural gas (CH_4) supplies the hydrogen and the nitrogen (N_2) is derived from the air. Ample amount of gas is used every year to produce ammonia. It can also be formed by using coal and other gasoline. Researchers are going on to replace urea by different organic fertilizer. Genetic change of crops can also be an option to reduce consumption of urea.

Captive Power: Captive Power Plant (CPP) is a plant which produces electricity for its owner's own uses or for a group for their own use. To shorten the gap between supply and demand of power in near future, incremental power is likely to be added from plants that are now undergoing overhaul, being constructed, in the process of being rented, or from captive power plants. While plant age remains a big challenge any unplanned plant shutdown may not be avoidable. The gas demand for power generation at present has reached nearly 1,200 MMCFD and Petrobangla can supply maximum 900 MMCFD for the power plants. In addition there are 1,800 MW capacity (installed) captive generators which accounts for approximately 300 MMCFD gas requirements. Unfortunately, majority of the captive power generators are not energy efficient and there are scopes for improvement in energy use in these plants. The total installed capacity of captive power plants in Bangladesh is estimated to be around 17% of the total installed capacity of the country. During FY 2012-2013, Gas based Captive Power Plants consumed about 3.235 billion CM. The installed capacity has exceeded 10,000 MW mark (10,264 MW in December, 2013) inclusive of 500 MW import from India through DC Regional inter connector. The captive power plants are mostly run by natural gas (70%) and the rest by HSD/HSFO (30%). The average efficiency of these plants is less than 30%, while the gas and steam turbines are even less. The investment costs per KW of Captive Power Plants are comparatively higher than the large capacity conventional power plants feeding power to the national grid. These single-cycle inefficient power plants if converted to combine cycle power plants, power generation can be enhanced approximately 1.5 times using the same amount of fuel gas. Unfortunately, the initiatives for conversion of the power plants to energy-efficient plants both for resource conservation and rational use of resources have been progressing slowly.

Household Sector: The household sector or domestic sector is incurred by the most number of customers and it consumes about 11% of the total natural gas produced. The Bangladesh

government's priority is to increase gas supply to power plants, followed by industries and fertilizer factories. Fresh household gas connections do not feature in the government's priority agenda. The domestic sector slowed down as piped gas connections to households were suspended from July 2010 to 2013. The authorities resumed piped natural gas connections to households because of increasing illegal connections and repeated pleas from the affected stakeholders to divert supplies from some power plants and fertilizer plants. Some 15 MMCFD of gas has been earmarked for new household gas connections. Still, the country is facing a huge gap in the supply and demand of natural gas in the household sector and the government is planning to import LPG to cope with gas supply shortfall.

Chapter Three:

Process Description

3. Process Description

Benzene production has several widely accepted production processes that are used throughout the world. Among them, catalytic reforming, toluene hydrodealkylation, toluene disproportionation and steam cracking are the mostly used processes. Benzene is naturally found in Volcanoes, Forest fires, Crude oil, Gasoline and Cigarette smoke.[39] It can be extracted profitably from the crude oil. Unfortunately, the global demand of benzene is so higher that we cannot rely on this one single crude oil extraction process. Again, this crude oil mines are not available in every country throughout the world. [40] Neither they're going to sustain forever. Hence, we have to find manufacturing process of benzene. But in the industrial manufacturing process, benzene is mostly prepared by hydrodealkylation of toluene. The companies that produce benzene in Bangladesh, such as Meghna Group, Tasnim Chemical, Meximco Limited, Fariza Trade International, mostly produce benzene through hydrodealkylation of benzene (HDA). One of the significant benefits of establishing benzene production plant for HDA process is, our availability of natural gas. The natural gas of Bangladesh is mostly 95-99% pure.[41] It generally doesn't contain sulfur. Therefore, we don't need to establish any desulfurizing unit. This will impact a huge relief in our establishment cost of the plant. Hence, we will get hydrogen at a cheaper cost. The other advantages of HDA process have been discussed back in the study background chapter.

The major raw materials of benzene production plant through hydrodealkylation are toluene and hydrogen. Toluene is extracted from crude oil. It is readily available in the market of Bangladesh. Besides, hydrogen is often reformed by steam-methane reforming. In the steam methane reforming, natural gas is used both as a fuel and a feed. The outlet of this plant is used as the raw material of benzene plant.

3.1 Hydrodealkylation Process Description

Toluene hydrodealkylation converts toluene to benzene. In this hydrogen-intensive process, toluene is mixed with hydrogen, then passed over a chromium catalyst at 500–650 °C and 20–60 atm pressure.[42] Under these conditions, toluene undergoes dealkylation to benzene and methane:

This irreversible reaction is accompanied by an equilibrium side reaction that produces diphenyl at higher temperature:

The yield of this reaction can exceed 95%.[44] The plant mainly consists one plug flow reactor (PFR), one pressure swing absorber (PSA), some distillation devices. We assume that the plant runs for 330days per year and 24hrs per day. We also assume that the production rate of our plant was 300ton Benzene/year.[45]

Fresh pure toluene is fed into the plant with negligible impurities. Hydrogen stream is fed into the plant consisting 95% (mole) hydrogen and 5% methane. The toluene stream enters at mixer-2 to mix with the recycle stream of toluene. Fresh hydrogen and toluene feed is fed at 5:1 ratio into the plant. The outlet stream of mixer-2 enters into mixer-1. In mixer-1, fresh hydrogen stream, recycled hydrogen stream and toluene stream is mixed and fed to the plug flow reactor (PFR) by passing it through the heat exchanger. The inlet temperature of the heat exchanger is 170°C.

The reactor conversion rate of 82% shows the best net present value. The selectivity is assumed to be 98%.[46] The inlet stream of the PFR reactor at 625.5°C contains toluene, hydrogen and slight amount of methane impurity caused by steam-methane reforming process. The outlet stream of this reactor contains benzene product, methane as biproduct, diphenyl produced by the side reaction, unreacted toluene and hydrogen.

The outlet stream of 580°C this PFR is to be fed into the flash drum by passing it through the heat exchanger-2. The flash drum should be operated at 170°C. It separates the benzene, toluene and diphenyl in the bottom stream from the methane and hydrogen consisting top stream. The temperature of the top stream of the flash drum remains at 170°C. But the bottom stream temperature falls at 88°C. It is again heated using the heat exchanger-3 to elevate the temperature at 274°C. At this temperature, the desired distillation is completed and the recycle stream also remains at near 170°C.[47]

To separate pure toluene, benzene and diphenyl, we have used two distillation columns by connecting one after another. The distillate of the first column contains 99.86% benzene and 0.14% of toluene. The bottom stream of the distillation column is fed to the distillation column-2. Pure

toluene distillate of this process is recycled, and fed to the mixer-2. The bottom stream of this column contains 81% of diphenyl and balance toluene.

The hydrogen and methane mixture are fed to the PSA to separate the methane completely so that the plant stays out of the risk of accumulation. The top stream of PSA consists pure hydrogen and the bottom stream consists 54% methane and balance hydrogen. The pure hydrogen top stream is recycled and fed into mixer-1. The recycle rate of Hydrogen gas is, $r = 1.4492 \text{ kmol H}_2 / \text{kmol H}_2$ removed.

3.2 Process Block Diagram (PBD) of Benzene Production Plant

The process block diagram of our discussed plant is shown on Figure 8. The diagram contains total 15 streams. The temperature and variables considered of these streams are expressed in a single Table-3.

Figure 8: Process block diagram of the hydroalkylation plant.

Table 3: Stream information of the process flow diagram.

Stream number	Flowrate Variables/compositions Considered for Calculation	Assumed Temperature (°C)
1	n_1 kmol /hour 0.95 mol H ₂ /mol 0.05 mol CH ₄ /mol	170
2	n_2 kmol Toluene/hour	170
3	n_3 kmol/hour 0.54 kmol CH ₄ /mol 0.46 kmol H ₂ /mol	170
4	n_4 kmol/hour 0.9986 kmol Benzene/mol 0.0014 kmol Toluene/mol	-
5	n_5 kmol/hour 0.81 kmol Diphenyl/mol 0.19 kmol Toluene/mol	-
6	n_6 kmol Toluene/hour	170
7	n_7 kmol Toluene/hour n_8 kmol /hour x_1 mol H ₂ /mol (1- x_1) mol CH ₄ /mol	170
8	n_7 kmol Toluene/hour n_8 kmol /hour x_1 mol H ₂ /mol (1- x_1) mol CH ₄ /mol	625.5
9	n_9 kmol Benzene/hour n_{10} kmol Toluene/hour n_{11} kmol H ₂ /hour n_{12} kmol CH ₄ /hour	580

	n_{13} kmol Diphenyl/hour	
10	n_9 kmol Benzene/hour n_{10} kmol Toluene/hour n_{11} kmol H_2 /hour n_{12} kmol CH_4 /hour n_{13} kmol Diphenyl/hour	170
11	n_{11} kmol H_2 /hour n_{12} kmol CH_4 /hour	170
12	n_9 kmol Benzene/hour n_{10} kmol Toluene/hour n_{13} kmol Diphenyl/hour	88
13	n_9 kmol Benzene/hour n_{10} kmol Toluene/hour n_{13} kmol Diphenyl/hour	274
14	n_{15} kmol Toluene/hour n_{13} kmol Diphenyl/hour	-
15	n_{14} kmol H_2 /hour	170
16	n_7 kmol Toluene/hour	170

3.3 Explanation of the Assumptions of the Benzene Production Plant

We will discuss the material balance and energy balance of this process block diagram on chapter 4. To perform the calculations perfectly, we need to ensure that the degree of freedom is zero by making necessary and relevant assumptions. In this sub-section, we will try to mention and justify those assumptions.

The hydrogen feed was not considered as pure feed. Instead of assuming it as pure feed, we have considered 5% of impurities of methane. It is assumed that the hydrogen feed we are going to use, was manufactured by steam-methane reforming. In a typical steam-methane reforming plant, the product stream always contains some amount of methane. This methane comes from the methane

feed of the plant. Again, the stream goes through a methanation process in order to remove even trace amount of carbon monoxide and carbon dioxide.

The hydrogen feed flowrate was considered as five times of the methane flow rate. Most of the industries has their own hydrogen plant to produce hydrogen. Hence, the hydrogen is generally considered as a cheaper raw material than toluene. Thus, by assuming this ratio, we focus on defining toluene as a limiting reactant. This ratio also helps us to reach at the 82% reaction conversion rate.[48]

Langqi considered conversion rate of 0.63, 0.72, 0.82, and 0.86 in the PFR reactor to commit hydrodealkylation and observed results for these reactor conversions in a matlab based simulation program generated by them. The result shows that the reactor conversion rate of 0.82 provide the best NPV. [48] Hence, we assume to achieve that conversion rate. The inlet temperature of this reactor for hydrodealkylation varies from 600-650°C. But to achieve this conversion rate, we will have to maintain the inlet and outlet temperature of the PFR reactor at 625°C and 580°C.

Chapter Four:

Calculations

4. Calculation

PFR balance:

Basis: 100 mol T/h feed

The desired reaction and the side reaction of this reactor are:

Assumptions:

This material balance requires three assumptions. Justification of these mentioned assumptions are given in the process description chapter.

- 1) $n_7 = 100$ kmol T/h
- 2) Single-pass reaction conversion = 0.82
- 3) Selectivity = 98%

Degree of Freedom Calculation:

Unknown = 8

Additional information = 3

Reactions = 2

DOF = 3

Single pass conversion is 0.82

$$n_9 = \frac{100 \text{ kmol T}}{\text{hr}} \left| \frac{0.82 \text{ mol B}}{1 \text{ mol T}} \right.$$
$$= 82 \text{ kmol B/hr}$$

Since the selectivity of Benzene with Diphenyl is 98%

$$n_{13} = \frac{82 \text{ kmol B}}{\text{hr}} \left| \frac{(100-98) \text{ mol D}}{98 \text{ mol B}} \right.$$
$$= 1.6735 \text{ kmol D/hr}$$

Methane produced,

$$n_{12} = n_9 + 2n_{13} = 85.347 \text{ kmol M/h}$$

Toluene remaining,

$$n_{10} = (n_7 - n_{12}) = 14.653 \text{ kmol T/h}$$

Flash Drum balance:

DOF analysis:

Unknown = 1

DOF = 1

Distillation Envelop Balance:

Benzene Balance:

$$n_4 \times 0.9986 = n_9$$

$$n_4 = 82.115 \text{ kmol/hr}$$

Diphenyl balance:

$$0.19 n_5 = n_{13}$$

$$n_5 = 8.808 \text{ kmol/hr}$$

Toluene Output:

$$0.0014 n_4 + 0.81 n_5 = 7.249$$

Toluene in the recycle stream,

$$n_6 = n_{10} - 7.249$$

$$= 14.653 - 7.249 \text{ kmol/h}$$

$$= 7.404 \text{ kmol/h}$$

Distillation Column-1 Balance:

Toluene Balance:

$$14.653 = 82 \times 0.0014 + n_{15}$$

$$n_{15} = 14.5382 \text{ kmol/hr}$$

Mixer 2 balance:

Mixer 2 balance:

$$n_2 + n_6 = n_7$$

$$n_2 = 100 - 7.404 \text{ kmol/h}$$

$$= 92.596 \text{ kmol/h}$$

PSA Balance:

Assumption:

1) Recycle rate of Hydrogen gas is, $r = 1.4492$ kmol H₂ / kmol H₂ removed

DOF Calculation:

Unknown = 3

Additional information = 1

Atomic balance = 2

DOF = 0

Methane Calculations

Methane balance:

$$0.54n_3 = n_{12}$$

$$n_3 = \frac{85.347}{0.54} \text{ kmol/h}$$

$$= 158.05 \text{ kmol/h}$$

$$n_{14} = \frac{158.05 \times 0.46}{1 \text{ kmol H}_2 \text{ removed}} \quad \left| \begin{array}{l} 1.4429 \text{ kmol H}_2 \\ \hline 1 \text{ kmol H}_2 \text{ removed} \end{array} \right.$$

$$= 104.909 \text{ kmol H}_2$$

H₂ balance:

$$n_{11} = 0.46n_3 + n_{14}$$

$$= (0.46 \times 158.05 + 104.909) \text{ kmol H}_2/\text{h}$$

$$= 177.612 \text{ kmol H}_2/\text{h}$$

Mixer 1 balance:

Assumption:

1) We need to provide the Hydrogen in such order so that the inlet ratio of T:H₂ remains 1:5

DOF Calculation:

Unknown = 3

Additional information = 1

Atomic balance = 2

DOF = 0

From the Assumption,

$$5n_2 = 0.95n_1$$

$$n_1 = 487.055 \text{ kmol/h}$$

Methane balance:

$$n_1 \times 0.05 = (1-x_1) \times n_8 \text{ -----(1)}$$

H₂ balance:

$$n_8x_1 = 0.95n_1 + n_{14}$$

$$n_8x_1 = 567.611 \text{ kmol -----(2)}$$

$$n_8 - n_8 x_1 = 24.35 \text{ -----(3)}$$

solving equation (2) and (3)

$$n_8 = 24.35 + 567.611$$

$$= 591.961 \text{ kmol/h}$$

$$x_1 = \frac{567.611}{n_8} = 0.9588 \text{ mol H}_2/\text{mol}$$

Our desired Benzene production(yearly) 300 k Ton/year

$$= \frac{300 \times 10^3 \times 10^3 \text{ kg}}{\text{yr}} \left| \frac{1 \text{ yr}}{330 \text{ d}} \right| \left| \frac{1 \text{ d}}{24 \text{ hr}} \right| \left| \frac{1 \text{ kmol B}}{78.11 \text{ kg B}} \right|$$

$$= 37.8787 \times 10^3 \text{ kg/hr}$$

Desired Benzene outlet,

$$n_4 = 484.311 \text{ kmol B/hr}$$

Now, our desired Benzene product is 484.341 kmol/hr

$$\text{So, } n_4 = 484.311 \text{ kmol/hr}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{multiplying factor, MF} &= \frac{484.311 \text{ kmol/hr}}{82.115 \text{ kmol/hr}} \\ &= 5.898 \end{aligned}$$

According this,

$$n_1 = 487.05 \times 5.898 = 2872.621 \text{ kmol/hr}$$

$$n_2 = 92.596 \times 5.898 = 546.13 \text{ kmol/hr}$$

$$n_3 = 158.05 \times 5.898 = 932.1789 \text{ kmol/hr}$$

$$n_4 = 484.311 \text{ kmol/hr}$$

$$n_5 = 8.808 \times 5.898 = 59.95 \text{ kmol/hr}$$

$$n_6 = 7.404 \times 5.898 = 43.668 \text{ kmol/hr}$$

$$x_1 = 0.9588 \text{ mol H}_2/\text{mol}$$

$$n_7 = 100 \times 5.898 = 589.8 \text{ kmol/hr}$$

$$n_8 = 591.961 \times 5.898 = 3491.386 \text{ kmol/hr}$$

$$n_9 = 82 \times 5.898 = 483.636 \text{ kmol/hr}$$

$$n_{10} = 14.653 \times 5.898 = 86.423 \text{ kmol/hr}$$

$$n_{11} = 554.5905 \times 5.898 = 3270.945 \text{ kmol/hr}$$

$$n_{12} = 85.347 \times 5.898 = 503.376 \text{ kmol/hr}$$

$$n_{13} = 1.6735 \times 5.898 = 9.87 \text{ kmol/hr}$$

$$n_{14} = 104.909 \times 5.898 = 618.75 \text{ kmol/hr}$$

$$n_{15} = 14.5382 \times 5.898 = 85.746 \text{ kmol/hr}$$

$$C_{p,T} = (94.18 \times 10^{-3} + 38 \times 10^{-5} T)$$

$$C_{p,H_2} = (28.84 \times 10^{-3} + 0.00765 \times 10^{-5} T)$$

$$C_{p,CH_4} = (34.31 \times 10^{-3} + 5.469 \times 10^{-5} T)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \Delta H = Q &= n_9 \int_{170}^{625} C_{p,T} \cdot dT + n_8 x_1 \int_{170}^{625} C_{p,H_2} \cdot dT + n_8 (1-x_1) \int_{170}^{625} C_{p,CH_4} \cdot dT \\
 &= n_9 \int_{170}^{625} (94.18 \times 10^{-3} + 38 \times 10^{-5} T) \cdot dT + n_8 x_1 \int_{170}^{625} (28.84 \times 10^{-3} + \\
 &0.00765 \times 10^{-5} T) \cdot dT + n_8 (1-x_1) \int_{170}^{625} (34.31 \times 10^{-3} + 5.469 \times 10^{-5} T) \cdot dT \\
 &= n_9 \times 111.58 + n_8 x_1 \times 13.136 + n_8 (1-x_1) \times 25.5 \\
 &= 101.605 \times 10^6 \text{ kJ/hr}
 \end{aligned}$$

Reference: 25°C , 1atm

Diphenyl \longrightarrow melting point = $69.2^\circ\text{C} / 70^\circ\text{C}$

Boiling point = 255°C

Enthalpy of phase transition (from crystalline to liquid) = 19.9 kJ/mol

Enthalpy of phase transition (from liquid to gas) = 52 kJ/mol

$C_{p,D}(\text{solid}), 25^\circ\text{C} = 197.7 \text{ J/mol}$

$C_{p,D}, 580^\circ\text{C} = 377.52 \text{ J/mol}$

Heat of formation (98.2 ± 2.5) kJ/mol

Reference: 25° C, 1 atm, H₂ (g), C (s),

Substances	Inlet		Outlet	
	\dot{n}_{in}	\widehat{H}_{in}	\dot{n}_{out}	\widehat{H}_{out}
Toluene	\dot{n}_7	\widehat{H}_1	\dot{n}_{10}	\widehat{H}_4
H ₂	$\dot{n}_8 x_1$	\widehat{H}_2	\dot{n}_{11}	\widehat{H}_5
CH ₄	$\dot{n}_8(1-x_1)$	\widehat{H}_3	\dot{n}_{12}	\widehat{H}_6
Benzene	0	0	\dot{n}_9	\widehat{H}_7
Diphenyl	0	0	\dot{n}_{13}	\widehat{H}_8

$$\widehat{H}_1 = \int_{625}^{110.62} (94.18 \times 10^{-3} + 38 \times 10^{-5}T) dT - 33.47 +$$

$$\int_{110.62}^{25} (148.8 \times 10^{-3} + 32.4 \times 10^{-5}T) dT = -168.43 \text{ kJ/mol}$$

$$\widehat{H}_4 = \int_{25}^{110.62} (148.8 \times 10^{-3} + 32.4 \times 10^{-5}T) dT + 33.47 +$$

$$\int_{110.62}^{580} (94.18 \times 10^{-3} + 38 \times 10^{-5}T) dT = 153.888 \text{ kJ/mol}$$

$$\widehat{H}_2 = \int_{625}^{25} (28.84 \times 10^{-3} + 0.00765 \times 10^{-5}T) dT = -17.32 \text{ kJ/mol}$$

$$\widehat{H}_3 = \int_{625}^{25} (34.31 \times 10^{-3} + 5.469 \times 10^{-5}T) dT = -31.2 \text{ kJ/mol}$$

$$\widehat{H}_5 = \int_{25}^{580} (28.84 \times 10^{-3} + 5.469 \times 10^{-5}T) dT = 16.019 \text{ kJ/mol}$$

$$\widehat{H}_6 = \int_{25}^{580} (34.31 \times 10^{-3} + 5.469 \times 10^{-5}T) dT = 28.224 \text{ kJ/mol}$$

$$\widehat{H}_7 = \int_{25}^{80.10} (126.5 \times 10^{-3} + 23.4 \times 10^{-5}T) dT + 30.765 + \int_{80.10}^{580} (74.06 \times 10^{-3} + 32.95 \times 10^{-5}T) dT = 129.8 \text{ kJ/mol}$$

$$\widehat{H}_8 = \int_{298}^{342.2} (0.1977) dT + 19.9 + \int_{342.2}^{528} (0.30) dT + 52.2 + \int_{528}^{853} (0.17) dT = 191.63 \text{ kJ/mol}$$

$$\widehat{H}_1 = 168.43 + 12 = 180.43 \text{ kJ/mol}$$

$$\widehat{H}_2 = 17.32 \text{ kJ/mol}$$

$$\hat{H}_3 = 31.25 - 74.85 = -43.6 \text{ kJ/mol}$$

$$\hat{H}_4 = 153.888 + 12 = 165.888 \text{ kJ/mol}$$

$$\hat{H}_5 = 16.019 \text{ kJ/mol}$$

$$\hat{H}_6 = 28.224 - 74.85 = -46.626 \text{ kJ/mol}$$

$$\hat{H}_7 = 129.8 + 48.66 = 178.46 \text{ kJ/mol}$$

$$\hat{H}_8 = 191.63 + 98.2 = 289.83 \text{ kJ/mol}$$

$$\begin{aligned}\Delta H = Q &= (n_{13}\hat{H}_8 + n_9\hat{H}_7 + n_{12}\hat{H}_6 + n_{11}\hat{H}_5 + n_{10}\hat{H}_4) - (n_8(1-x_1)\hat{H}_3 + n_{8x_1}\hat{H}_2 + n_7\hat{H}_1) \\ &= -25.6 \times 10^6 \text{ kJ}\end{aligned}$$

$$\hat{H}_D = \int_{853}^{528} (0.170) dT - 52 + \int_{528}^{438} (0.30) dT = -134.25 \text{ kJ/mol}$$

$$\hat{H}_T = \int_{580}^{165} (94.18 \times 10^{-3} + 38 \times 10^{-5} T) dT = -97.828 \text{ kJ/mol}$$

$$\hat{H}_B = \int_{580}^{165} (74.05 \times 10^{-3} + 32.95 \times 10^{-5} T) dT = -81.667 \text{ kJ/mol}$$

$$\hat{H}_{\text{Hydrogen}} = \int_{580}^{165} (28.84 \times 10^{-3} + 0.00765 \times 10^{-5} T) dT = -11.98 \text{ kJ/mol}$$

$$\hat{H}_{\text{Methane}} = \int_{580}^{165} (34.31 \times 10^{-3} + 5.469 \times 10^{-5} T) dT = -22.69 \text{ kJ/mol}$$

$$\Delta H = Q = n_9 \hat{H}_B + n_{10} \hat{H}_T + n_{11} \hat{H}_{\text{Hydrogen}} + n_{12} \hat{H}_{\text{Methane}} + n_{13} \hat{H}_D = -99.88 \times 10^6 \text{ kJ}$$

Energy Balance on Heat Exchanger-3:

$$\begin{aligned} Q &= \{483.626 \times (-24.868) + 86.423 \times (-2.05) + 9.87 \times (27.427)\} \text{ kJ/hr} \\ &= -11.933 \times 10^6 \text{ kJ/hr} \end{aligned}$$

Chapter Five:

Environmental Impact and

Waste Management

5. Environmental Impact and Waste Management

The biproduct of this plant are methane and diphenyl. The process doesn't produce carbon dioxide, carbon monoxide or any other oxide compounds of sulfur or nitrogen in a mentionable quantity. Atleast the design of the plant doesn't allow such kind of production. But the biproducts, i.e., methane and diphenyl have a high environmental risk. It can never be allowed to release the methane or diphenyl in the environment at a very small quantity. Instead of releasing it into the environment, we can use these components by converting them into other different compounds. We can also sell these substances since they have a high global market demand. The environmental risk and market demand of these compounds are discussed below.

5.1 Health Hazard of Diphenyl

Diphenyl is highly toxic chemical. It is carcinogenic and has so many other health hazards. High levels of diphenyl exposure in workers cause eye and skin irritation, along with toxic effects on the liver, kidneys, and central and peripheral nervous systems. Symptoms include headaches, gastrointestinal pain, nausea, limb numbness, and fatigue. Animal tests show moderate acute toxicity through ingestion and low to moderate toxicity through dermal exposure.

EPA deems existing mouse and rat studies inadequate. While one mouse study showed no increased tumor rates, another found tumors in treated and control rats, unrelated to biphenyl. Biphenyl is classified as Group D by EPA, not classifiable as to human carcinogenicity.

The RfD is an estimate (with uncertainty spanning perhaps an order of magnitude) of a daily oral exposure to the human population (including sensitive subgroups) that is likely to be without appreciable risk of deleterious non cancer effects during a lifetime. It is not a direct estimator of risk but rather a reference point to gauge the potential effects. At exposures increasingly greater than the RfD, the potential for adverse health effects increases. Lifetime exposure above the RfD does not imply that an adverse health effect would necessarily occur.

Chronic exposure in humans mainly causes central nervous system problems like fatigue, headache, tremors, insomnia, sensory impairment, and mood changes. In animal studies, kidney effects are prominent in rats chronically exposed to diphenyl through ingestion. EPA hasn't set a Reference Concentration (RfC) for diphenyl. The Reference Dose (RfD) stands at 0.05 mg/kg/d based on rat kidney damage, serving as a guide for oral exposure levels without significant non-

cancerous effects. Exposure exceeding the RfD heightens the risk of adverse health effects, but it doesn't guarantee their occurrence. EPA has high confidence in the primary study used for RfD determination, though supporting data are limited, leading to medium confidence in the RfD. There are no reproductive or developmental impacts in humans. Limited animal data suggest biphenyl doesn't induce birth defects. Some fetotoxicity signs were observed in rats exposed to high gavage levels of biphenyl, though not significant.

5.2 Diphenyl Market

The global diphenyl market, valued at \$1.24 billion in 2021, is projected to reach \$1.98 billion by 2031, with a compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of 4.8% from 2022 to 2031. Biphenyl, a clear and colourless organic compound. It is prized for its antifungal and antimicrobial properties, finding extensive use as a heat transfer medium and in organic synthesis. Additionally, it serves as a dye carrier in the textile industry, improving fabric quality.

The demand for packed food items, spurred by busy lifestyles and changing consumer preferences, is driving the use of biphenyl to prevent fungal growth. For example, the Indian packaged food market is expected to double in 5-10 years, reaching \$70 billion, potentially boosting the biphenyl market. Moreover, population growth and urbanization are fueling demand for various consumer goods, where biphenyl serves as a key chemical intermediate.

However, prolonged exposure to biphenyls and their derivatives can cause health issues such as eye, liver, and skin irritations, as well as kidney and cardiovascular disorders. This may impede market growth, particularly in industries with high exposure levels.

Conversely, the pharmaceutical sector is experiencing significant growth due to the rising incidence of diseases. Biphenyls are widely used in treating various health disorders, including hypertension, diabetes, arthritis, Alzheimer's, and cancer, presenting lucrative opportunities for the market.

The biphenyl market is segmented by source (crude oil, coal tar, natural gas), application (dye carrier, food & beverages, pharmaceutical solvents), and region (North America, Europe, Asia-Pacific, LAMEA).

5.3 Impact of Methane in Climate Change

Methane is responsible for around 30% of the rise in global temperatures since the industrial revolution, and rapid and sustained reductions in methane emissions are key to limit near-term warming and improve air quality. Two key characteristics determine the impact of different greenhouse gases on the climate: the length of time they remain in the atmosphere and their ability to absorb energy. Methane has a much shorter atmospheric lifetime than carbon dioxide (CO₂) – around 12 years compared with centuries. But it absorbs much more energy while it exists in the atmosphere.

Methane also affects air quality because it can lead to ground-level (tropospheric) ozone, a dangerous air pollutant. Methane leaks can also pose explosion hazards.

The concentration of methane in the atmosphere is currently around two-and-a-half times greater than its pre-industrial levels. The increase has accelerated in recent years, and preliminary analysis indicates 2021's rise is likely to be amongst the largest ever recorded.

Estimates of methane emissions are subject to a high degree of uncertainty, but the most recent comprehensive assessment – provided in the Global Methane Budget – suggests that annual global methane emissions are around 580 Mt. These include emissions from natural sources (around 40% of emissions), and the remaining 60% which originate from human activity, known as anthropogenic emissions.

The largest anthropogenic source is agriculture, responsible for around one-quarter of emissions, closely followed by the energy sector, which includes emissions from coal, oil, natural gas and biofuels.

5.4 Steam of Hot Water Release Requirements to Environment

The release of steam or hot water into the environment is subject to various regulations and requirements to ensure environmental protection and public health. Some key considerations include:

1. Temperature Limits:

Regulations may stipulate maximum allowable temperatures for the release of steam or hot water to prevent thermal pollution and avoid harming aquatic ecosystems. These limits vary depending on factors such as the receiving water body and the sensitivity of local ecosystems.

2. Chemical Composition:

The chemical composition of the steam or hot water, including any contaminants or pollutants, must meet regulatory standards to prevent water pollution and protect environmental quality. Monitoring and testing may be required to ensure compliance with these standards.

3. Discharge Permits:

Industries may need permits or approvals from regulatory authorities to discharge steam or hot water into the environment. These permits typically specify discharge limits, monitoring requirements, and reporting obligations to ensure compliance with environmental regulations.

4. Mitigation Measures:

Industries may be required to implement mitigation measures to minimize the environmental impact of steam or hot water discharges. This could include measures such as cooling towers or heat exchangers to reduce the temperature of discharged water or treatment systems to remove contaminants before discharge.

5. Ecological Impact Assessment:

Before discharging steam or hot water into sensitive environments, industries may need to conduct ecological impact assessments to evaluate potential effects on aquatic ecosystems, wildlife, and habitat. These assessments help identify potential risks and inform mitigation strategies to minimize environmental harm.

6. Public Notification:

Industries may be required to provide public notification or consultation regarding planned steam or hot water discharges, particularly in areas where there may be concerns about potential environmental impacts or public health risks. Transparency and communication with stakeholders are essential for fostering community trust and addressing concerns.

By adhering to these requirements and implementing appropriate management practices, industries can minimize the environmental impact of steam or hot water discharges and ensure compliance with regulatory standards, thereby safeguarding environmental quality and public health.

Chapter Six:

Market Analysis of Benzen

6. Market Analysis of Benzene

Benzene is a common feedstock for several compounds used in automobiles, textiles, and medicines, among other sectors. Benzene is utilised as an intermediate chemical in the manufacturing of nylons, polymers, resins, and synthetic textiles. The primary methods of producing benzene are naphtha pyrolysis and steam cracking, toluene hydrodealkylation, naphtha reforming catalytically, toluene disproportionation, and biomass toluene deprotonation. . They are made from derivatives such as ethylbenzene, cumene, alkylbenzene, aniline, chlorobenzene, cyclohexane, and maleic anhydride. Benzene is used in rubber lubricants, plastics, resins, and synthetic fibers. Furthermore, the COVID-19 pandemic has had an unparalleled and noteworthy effect, leading to a detrimental demand shock for benzene and its derivatives in several industries. Benzene Market Drivers Benzene Market Segmentation Global Benzene Market Segmentation, 4 Derivative by Usage, Benzene Market Restraints, Benzene Market Global Analysis, Benzene Market Global Analysis, Benzene Market Analysis and Size are depicted below.

6.1 Benzene Market Drivers

The increase in disposable income is the key growth factor in the worldwide gasoline industry. Benzene, an aromatic hydrocarbon, is flammable. Benzene is very flammable and readily dissolves in the atmosphere. Volcanoes and forest fires, for example, naturally pollute the atmosphere with benzene. Common sources of benzene in the interior environment include glues, paints, furniture waxes, and detergents. It is mainly used in the manufacture of polystyrene and the synthesis of

phenol and aniline. Benzene can be found in gasoline, synthetic rubber, plastics, industrial solvents, and paint. Benzene is very poisonous and carcinogenic.

6.2 Global Benzene Market Segmentation

This term paper focuses on revenue growth at global, regional, and country levels and provides an analysis of the latest industry trends in each of the sub-segments from 2018 to 2030. For this study, Grand View Research has segmented the global benzene market report based on derivative by end-use, production process, and region:

Figure 9: Benzene Market Report Segmentation.[49]

6.3 Derivative by Usage

Global Benzene and its Derivatives Market Share, By Application, 2020

Figure 10: Global Benzene and its Derivatives Market Share.[50]

In spite of being a carcinogenic material, benzene is having an extremely wide range of usage. Benzene ring is found in almost every component highly used in the modern civilization. Figure 10 shows that benzene shares most of the market share in the industries and oil-gas industry. It is even used in pharmaceutical products.

6.4 Benzene Market Restraints

However, the expansion of the industry will be hampered by strict environmental laws and volatility in raw material prices. The major constraint of this market is that exposure to benzene can cause harm to people in multiple ways. The severity of injuries or the degree of symptoms caused by benzene exposure is determined by the amount of benzene ingested and the length of time individuals are exposed to it

Global Benzene Market – Industry Trends and Forecast to 2030

Market Size in USD Billion

CAGR - 3%

Forecast Period	2022–2030
Market Size (Base Year)	USD 48.65 Billion
Market Size (Forecast Year)	USD 62.55 Billion
CAGR	3%

Figure 11: Global Benzene Market - Industry trends and forecast to 2030.

6.5 Benzene Market Analysis and Size

Growing phenol consumption and rising demand for methylene diphenyl diisocyanate are key drivers driving the global benzene market from 2023 to 2030. The growing demand for polyester in areas including textiles, packaging, and automotive is driving market development.

Data Bridge Market Research analyses that the global benzene market, which was USD 48.65 billion in 2022, is expected to reach USD 62.55 billion by 2030, growing at a CAGR of 3.0% during the forecast period of 2023 to 2030. In addition to the insights on market scenarios such as market value, growth rate, segmentation, geographical coverage, and major players, the market reports curated by the Data Bridge Market Research also include in-depth expert analysis, geographically represented company-wise production and capacity, network layouts of distributors and partners, detailed and updated price trend analysis and deficit analysis of supply chain and demand.

6.5.1 Benzene Market Regional Analysis

In 2024, the Asia-Pacific accounts for the largest market share in Benzene Market. Asia Pacific dominated the market with a revenue share of 45.2% in 2022. This is attributed to the expanding end-use industries such as the chemical industry, packaging, automobile, pharmaceutical, and others in the region. According to International Institute for Sustainable Development (IISD) in 2021, the chemical industry in the Asia Pacific accounted for around 45% of global chemical manufacturing and 7% of global GDP.

Figure 12: Asia Pacific Benzene and its Derivatives Market Size.[51]

The major consumers and producers of benzene in the Asia Pacific are China, India, South Korea, and Japan. China is among the major consumer of benzene with imports amounting to USD 2,785,449 thousand whereas, South Korea accounted for major export amounting to USD 2,254,945 thousand in 2021. The increase in demand and import in China is due to the increasing usage of benzene in construction and automobile products such as paints, flooring, fiberglass,

adhesives, tires, and others. According to the National Bureau of Statistics in China in 2021, the construction output of China accounted for around USD 4,091 Billion. Thus, the increasing end-use industries in the country are further driving the demand for the product.

Figure 13: Benzene Market trends by region.[51]

North America is also expected to witness growth during the forecast period due to the increasing packaging, petrochemical, and pharmaceutical industries which are the major end users of the product. According to the U.S. Department of Health & Human Services, benzene is widely used and ranked among the top 20 chemicals for production volume in the country.

Europe is also anticipated to witness growth but at a relatively slower rate compared to North America and Asia Pacific due to tightening government regulations for use of benzene or its derivatives in consumer goods. For instance, the regulations imposed by the European Chemicals Agency (ECHA) and other organizations prohibiting the marketing and use of benzene in case it is present in mixtures or other substances at or above a concentration of 0.1% by weight are acting as a restraining factor in the growth of benzene in the region.

6.5.2 Benzene Market Global Analysis

Global Benzene Market, By Derivative (Alkyl Benzene, Cumene, Cyclohexane, Ethyl Benzene, Nitro Benzene, Others), End-Use Industry (Construction, Transportation, Medical, Pulp and Paper, Automobile Industries, Packaging, Textile) - Industry Trends and Forecast to 2023 to 2030.

Figure 14: Global Benzene Market by Regions 2023 to 2030.[52]

6.6 Key Companies & Market Share Insights

The market is highly competitive with the presence of some major industry players dominating the market. The market is characterized by the adoption of various strategic initiatives such as increasing production capacity, and technology partnerships to gain a competitive edge. For instance, companies such as Hongyi Petrochemical, in 2021, announced to set up a naphtha cracker that will add 80,000 TPA benzene capacity along with other products. This expansion will result in strengthening the position of the company. Some of the prominent players in the benzene market include: Dow, INEOS Group, LyondellBasell Industries Holdings B.V., BASF SE, Royal Dutch Shell Plc, Reliance Industries Limited, Chevron Phillips Chemical Company LLC, China Petrochemical Corporation, Marathon Petroleum Corporation, LG etc.

6.9 Recent Development

In March 2022, INEOS agreed to buy a 50% stake in Shanghai SECCO Petrochemical Company Ltd. This is a subsidiary of China Petroleum and Chemical Corporation. SECCO now produces 4.2 MMT of petrochemicals, including ethylene, propylene, polyethylene, polypropylene, styrene, polystyrene, butadiene, benzene, and toluene. The 200-hectare property is in Shanghai's Chemical Industry Park. The firm will be able to develop its footprint in China.

In February 2021, Hengyi Petrochemical announced to build a benzene plant to raise the yearly capacity from 500 kilotons to 800 kilotons. Through this action, the corporation hopes to grow its petrochemical division.

April 2021-Iran achieved self-sufficiency in benzene production. According to a statement from the Iranian Oil Ministry, the Iranian petrochemical industry now completely meets domestic demand for benzene, and Iran will no longer require benzene imports. The Bu Ali Sina Petrochemical Company (BSPC) attained its maximum output of 85,610 thousand tons of benzene in March, achieving 100% of its production capacity.

January 2021 - Sinopec and Lyondell Basell finalized a joint venture in China to produce propylene oxide and styrene monomer. Both the companies signed an agreement to create a 50-50 joint venture to primarily cater to increasing demand for propylene oxide and styrene monomer in China's domestic market. The joint venture will use Lyondell Basell's advanced technology to

build a new facility in Zhenhai, Ningbo, China, capable of producing 600 kilotons of styrene monomer per year.[53]

Chapter Seven:

Conclusion

7. Conclusion

Since benzene is a carcinogenic compound, everyone has an intention to replace benzene with other similar type of products. Yet, in modern era, benzene has captured a very huge market on the global perspective. It is used in both laboratory scale and industry scale. Benzene is a raw material of a lot of important daily products that we use very often in our lives. To fulfill its huge demand, we cannot rely only on the crude oil extraction process. We often prefer to fulfill majority of the benzene demand by chemical synthesis.

Among all the mentioned processes, hydrodealkylation is the most suitable process for the industries of Bangladesh. The raw materials of this process are hydrogen and toluene. We expect to collect pure toluene from crude oil and synthesize hydrogen from steam-methane reforming plant of hydrogen. We assumed a 95% pure hydrogen fresh feed stream with balance methane. We have taken some relevant assumptions to perform the material and energy balance calculations. The process calculation yields all expected results which proves that the assumptions taken were relevant.

The product of this plant is 99.86% benzene with balance toluene. Our plant ensures 300tons of yearly benzene production. To perform our calculation, we have assumed that the plant runs 330days per year and 24hour per day. The biproduct streams contains 19% diphenyl solution with balance toluene and 56% methane with balance hydrogen solution. These biproduct streams can be later purified and converted into other compounds. The effluent hydrogen and toluene can be recycled and used in the process later. To fulfill the yearly supply requirement, we will have to ensure 2872.621kmol/hr of hydrogen feed flow rate and 546.13kmol/hr of toluene feed flow rate at operating condition.

Definitely the product and the byproduct of this plant is extremely sensitive for the environment. None of them should be allowed to leak or release in the environment intentionally. The design of the plant doesn't allow to release any substance at the environment. Yet, there are some possible flaws that can be considered as the limitations of the assumptions. Most of the assumptions were taken on behalf of the references of simulation-based papers instead of real papers. This is may be proven as a major flaw while executing the plant. Moreover, we didn't consider any leakage or make up feed in this process. We have considered chromium as a catalyst of our PFR reactor. The make up catalyst process wasn't taken under consideration in this paper in this paper.

Reference

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